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**QA4EO: Support to cloud mask validation for CMIX
Roadmap - Plan for up-scaling**

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Table of contents

1. INTRODUCTION	4
1.1 OBJECTIVE	4
1.2 SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT	4
2. REQUIREMENTS AND STATE OF THE ART ANALYSIS	5
2.1 VALIDATION REQUIREMENTS	5
2.1.1 LITERATURE RESEARCH ON BASIC EO BASED THEMATIC VALIDATION REQUIREMENTS AND EXISTING APPROACHES	5
2.1.2 LITERATURE RESEARCH ON EXISTING CLOUD MASK VALIDATION DATASETS AND METHODS	8
2.1.3 FINDINGS FROM CLOUD MASK INTERCOMPARISON EXERCISE (CMIX)	10
2.1.4 REQUIREMENTS DEPENDING ON APPLICATIONS	11
2.1.4.1 Applications with non-cloud conservative needs	12
2.1.4.2 Applications with cloud conservative needs	12
2.1.4.3 Applications with balanced needs	12
2.2 MEASUREMENT REQUIREMENTS	12
2.2.1 TEMPORAL REQUIREMENTS	13
2.2.1.1 Monitoring frequencies	13
2.2.1.2 Data availability for further analysis	13
2.2.2 SPATIAL REQUIREMENTS	13
2.2.2.1 Sampling unit - data resolution	13
2.2.2.2 Geometric accuracy - comparability of the validated object	13
2.2.2.3 Sample size	13
2.2.2.4 Global site distribution	15
2.2.3 THEMATIC REQUIREMENTS	15
2.2.4 SPECTRAL REQUIREMENTS	15
2.3 ANALYSIS REQUIREMENTS	16
2.3.1 QUALITY OF THE REFERENCE DATASET	16
2.3.2 QUANTITATIVE VERSUS QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS	16
2.4 INSTRUMENTATION STATE OF THE ART	17
2.4.1 OVERVIEW OF MONITORING NETWORKS	17
2.4.1.1 Cloudnet	17
2.4.1.2 ACTRIS network – Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure	18
2.4.1.3 Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) - cloud mode observations	18

2.4.1.4 Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) Program	18
2.4.2 OVERVIEW OF GROUND-BASED CLOUD MONITORING INSTRUMENTS	19
2.4.2.1 Radar	19
2.4.2.2 Lidar	20
2.4.2.3 Ceilometer	20
2.4.2.4 Sky cameras	21
3. EVALUATION OF REQUIREMENTS	25
4. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS FROM D2 (OPERATIONS AND VALIDATION REPORT)	26
5. ROADMAP	27
5.1 DEVELOPMENT PHASES	27
5.1.1 PHASE 1: OBTAINING LEVEL OF MATURITY	27
5.1.2 PHASE 2: EUROPEAN EXTENSION – TOWARDS SELF-SUFFICIENCY	28
5.1.3 PHASE 3: EUROPEAN ROLL OUT	28
5.1.4 PHASE 4: GLOBAL ROLL OUT	28
6. REFERENCES	29

1. Introduction

1.1 Objective

In the scope of the QA4EO Project undertaken by ESA, a work package “QA4EO WP 2185 - Support to cloud mask validation for CMIX” had been executed. The objective of this work package had been defined to prepare for establishing and for operating a network of cloud mask validation sites. Based on the experience in Europe (Rome site – La Sapienza University) and the United States of America (Goddard site – Goddard Space Flight Center) a concept for instrumentation and operations had been initially developed and tested.

The goal of this work package was to prototype algorithms and methods to process data and compare them with satellite algorithms for cloud masking. A critical requirement is the cloud base. There are two approaches that have been planned to be compared: using stereo sky camera data (US) and a ceilometer (Rome). The Rome site was upgraded and received 2 sky cameras identical to the US site.

This WP will be a proof-of-concept, delivering a plan for global upscaling. The work package included 4 tasks and delivered a report on the experiences of this experiment and the results of the cloud screening validation at the example of Sentinel 3 OLCI and Sentinel 2 MSI. Additionally, a roadmap towards a global network was developed which is this document.

1.2 Scope of the document

The scope of this document is to outline the requirements for a good cloud mask validation and a roadmap for global upscaling of a sky camera network for cloud mask validation.

2. Requirements and state of the art analysis

This section will present the findings from WP 2185 task 1 - Requirements and state of the art analysis. The goal is to define the requirements for validating cloud masks of remotely sensed satellite data, as well as the requirements on the ground-based measurements and requirements for the analysis. To give an overview of current ground-based cloud monitoring a section on instrumentation state-of-the-art will give information on existing global networks or sky cameras and available sky-cameras itself, as well as the current instruments at the Rome and Goddard site.

2.1 Validation Requirements

The goal of this section is the attempt to define the requirements for validating cloud masks of remotely sensed data. The word attempt is used here as there are a few obstacles on the way to validating a cloud mask.

First a cloud is not a “binary” object that is 0% or 100% obstructing a satellite’s view to the ground, or better obstructing the reflected sunlight to the sensor, but anything in between.

Second, the object that is analysed (the cloud) is located in the sky, multiple meters to tenths of kilometres away from the earth surface, extending from a few tenths of meters to hundreds of kilometres. Therefore, a direct (in-situ) measure of the target cannot be achieved with high repetition and for complete areas. The most common technique to monitor clouds, apart from geostationary satellites, are ground based sky sensors (Radar, Lidar, Microwave radiometers as well as sky cameras). As these are also indirect measures of the target, compared to satellite remote sensing, this means that any “truth” derived from these ground-based sensors can also only be defined as another reference for comparison but not the “truth” as an in-situ measurement would.

Third, the requirements for a cloud detection will vary depending on the application. While some applications can handle a certain number of undetected clouds, or cloud contamination, other applications would fail.

To address these obstacles and define requirements as best as possible, this section will start with a general literature research on classification validation (section 2.1.1) and also highlight some more recent approaches taken on validation of cloud masks derived from remotely sensed data (section 0.)

2.1.1 Literature research on basic EO based thematic validation requirements and existing approaches

When creating a cloud mask based on remotely sensed data, a classification of the data is conducted. In principle the output can be perceived as some kind of map, since it has classes (minimum: cloud and non-cloud) and represents space on the earth surface, even if the data is potentially still in satellite coordinates (e.g. Sentinel-3 OLCI L1/L2). Therefore, the development in map validation has to be considered as a basis for the analysis of requirements for remotely sensed cloud mask validation. For a very long time, accuracy assessment of maps has not been given a great importance, until the 1970s. Hord and Brooner (1976), van Genderen and Lock (1977), and Ginevan (1979) proposed a set of criteria and techniques for testing map accuracy. Continued in the early 1980s, with the increase of digitization of maps, more in-depth studies have been conducted and more sophisticated methods had been proposed (Rosenfield et al., 1982; Congalton et al., 1983; Aronoff, 1985), leading to the error matrix and Cohen’s Kappa becoming the standard for reporting remotely sensed data classification accuracies (Story and Congalton, 1986, Cohen, 1960). With increase of digitization and followed increase in map production, requirements and methods for validation have evolved, including definitions and requirements for sampling schemes and sample sizes, classification schemes, and spatial autocorrelation. In 1991 Congalton made a detailed overview of techniques and considerations for accuracy assessment. Since methods for assessment had been matured already in the early 1990s, other important considerations became evident, like ground verification techniques, incorporating assessments into regional and global projects, and evaluating all the sources of error in the spatial data.

The goal of all assessments is to define the thematic accuracy of any classification. Therefore, it important to define this accuracy first. Thematic accuracy describes the relationship of a mapped class of a remotely sensed pixel to a defined “truth” reference for the respective pixel. To ensure a meaningful result, all reference data (in this case pixels) must be correct or at least knowledge about the accuracy of the reference data is needed to allow a fair comparison with meaningful results (Congalton, 2007). Congalton (1991) points out that, “Although no reference data set may be

completely accurate, it is important that the reference data have high accuracy or else it is not a fair assessment. Therefore, it is critical that the ground or reference data collection be carefully considered in any accuracy assessment.”

Further Congalton (1991) stated that the following factors must be considered to generate a valid confusion/error matrix:

1. Reference data collection.
2. Classification scheme.
3. Sampling scheme
4. Spatial autocorrelation
5. Sample size and sample unit

Not considering one of these factors could already lead to significant shortcomings in the accuracy assessment. The five points in relation to cloud mask validation will be addressed briefly.

Reference data collection:

Reference data collection is the most important factor and first step in any assessment procedure. The significance of the assessment is depending on the correctness of the reference. There are multiple ways of creating a reference data collection. Each collection method adds a certain bias to the reference. This bias needs to be known and kept as low as possible. Since the method for this study is already defined, the classification of the sky camera images must be assessed accordingly.

Classification scheme:

The classification scheme of the classification (algorithm output) and the reference data must be identical. Not in all cases the reference has the same classification scheme, and a reclassification is needed before validation. By reclassifying reference data or algorithm outputs, a certain bias is introduced into the validation results. Especially if the definition of the classes is not 100% identical. In case of validating a reference against multiple algorithm outputs, all algorithm outputs must have identical classes which are identically defined, to ensure a precise comparability.

Sampling scheme:

This factor is not of a big importance for this study, as only two classes (cloud vs. non-cloud) are examined. Nevertheless, it should be noted that when validating multiple classes, knowledge of the distribution of the classes in the algorithm output should be considered. A stratified random sampling approach is normally considered to be the most useful approach. When using sky camera images as a reference, this approach is less feasible, as these sampling approaches start from the classification (algorithm output). The sky camera validation approach will be designed as a fixed reference for multiple algorithm outputs. Thus, the sampling is defined by the reference and not the classification to be validated. Or in short, the methodology cannot be applied in the case of sky camera observations. Nevertheless, the distribution of the classes and samples in relation to the validated product need to be considered when analysing the assessment result. Since maps are usually considered when analysing a sampling scheme, a consistent global classification is not. But a consistent global classification is the output of a cloud mask algorithm of satellite based remotely sensed data. Thus, stratification can also be achieved e.g., by using average global cloud distributions.

Another complication lies in the transition of a classification, if the classes are not simply “binary”, like transparent clouds/cloud borders. Nevertheless, the transition between cloud and non-cloud poses most of the time the biggest problem to users as well as cloud mask producers (algorithms).

Spatial Autocorrelation

Congalton (2007) states: “Because of sensor resolution, landscape variability, and other factors, remotely sensed data are often spatially autocorrelated. Spatial autocorrelation involves a dependency between neighbouring pixels such that a certain quality or characteristic at one location has an effect on that same quality or characteristic at neighbouring locations (Cliff and Ord 1973, Congalton 1988a). Spatial autocorrelation can affect the result of an accuracy assessment if an error in a certain location can be found to influence errors positively or negatively in surrounding locations. The best way to minimize spatial autocorrelation is to impose some minimum distance between sample units.”

This factor mostly needs to be considered when analysing sky camera-based reference data. If not only the centre pixel of the camera is used, but the sampled pixels are also all located around the sky camera location and thus spatially autocorrelated. Only a big global network of sky-cameras will counteract this circumstance.

Sample Size and Sample Unit:

For the size of the samples a general rule of thumb is to use a minimum of 50 to 100 samples per class. Using this rule each class can be assessed individually (Congalton & Green, 1999). This requirement needs some more interpretation for a sky camera based approach, especially if a global dataset based on medium to high resolution sensors is validated.

The sample unit factor poses the biggest challenge, since the validated object is placed vertically between the two observation sources (satellite sensor and sky camera) and thus huge geometric differences need to be considered.

Note:

Sample unit is the size of the sample. If you are dealing with in-situ data collected in the field, this is important. For example, if you are validating a LC map with a pixel resolution of 30m. Assuming you did not use any minimum mapping unit above this your in-situ samples should at least cover 900m², to represent your classification properly.

After nearly 20 years of evolution in remotely sensed data validation Congalton and Green (2019) published a very comprising summary of requirements, methods and techniques for accuracy assessment of remotely sensed data. Congalton states that there are a few important questions that need to be asked and considered, when designing and implementing an accuracy assessment. In short these questions include:

1. Questions concerning the design of an accuracy assessment sample:
 - What are the map classes to be assessed and how are they distributed across the landscape?
 - What is the appropriate sampling unit?
 - How many samples should be taken?
 - How should the samples be chosen?

2. Questions concerning how the reference data should be collected:
 - What should be the source of the reference data?
 - How should the reference data be collected?
 - When should the reference data be collected?
 - How do I ensure consistency and objectivity in my data collection?

3. Questions concerning how the analysis should be conducted:
 - What are the different analysis techniques for continuous as compared to discontinuous map data?
 - What is an error matrix and how should it be used?
 - What are the statistical properties associated with the error matrix and what analysis techniques are applicable?
 - What is fuzzy accuracy and how can you conduct a fuzzy accuracy assessment?
 - How is accuracy assessment conducted on change detection maps?
 - How is accuracy assessment conducted on maps created from multiple layers of data?

These questions include the 5 factors described before, but also address additional requirements. This list of questions later will be used to check the suitability of the sky camera approach for cloud mask validation. However, a quite important criterion seems to be missing, since most of the validated products are mono temporal, is the distribution of the reference dataset in time.

2.1.2 Literature research on existing cloud mask validation datasets and methods

In this section, research on the most common freely available reference datasets for cloud mask validation is presented, as well as a short overview of studies using different sources to generate a reference for cloud mask validation.

Validation Datasets

Within the last 10 years the free availability of high-resolution data satellite data (Sentinel-2, Landsat 8), repetition cycles of HR sensors (Sentinel-2 A & B), as well as storage and processing capabilities have increased strongly. This development has stimulated the development of a great variety of cloud masking algorithms for these sensors using very different methodologies, from classic spectral tests to decision tree approaches or machine learning. The methodologies are not only based on mono-temporal approaches, but now also include multitemporal approaches, due to the high repetition cycles. When creating new cloud masking algorithms reference data is needed, either for training of a classifier or for a validation, to prove the performance of a developed algorithm. Thus, within the last 10 year multiple reference datasets have been created, which include for example:

- Landsat 8 SPARCS (Hughes & Hayes 2014)
- L8 Biome (U.S. Geological Survey 2016, Foga et al. 2017)
- Landsat 8 Collection 2 cloud truth mask validation set (Scaramuzza 2021)
- An experimental sky-image-derived cloud validation dataset for Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 satellites over NASA GSFC (Skakun et al. 2020b)
- PixBox Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 pixel collections for CMIX (Paperin et al. 2021a, Paperin et al. 2021b)
- Database File of Manually classified Sentinel-2A Data (Hollstein et al. 2016)
- Sentinel-2 Cloud Mask Catalogue (Francis et al. 2020)
- Sentinel-2 reference cloud masks generated by an active learning method (Baetens & Hagolle 2018)

The above list includes the best-known datasets used and designed for training and validation of Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 data. A bit more detail about these datasets will be given to show the purpose and design of the datasets to help shaping the requirements for a good cloud validation dataset.

Landsat 8 SPARCS cloud validation masks dataset (Hughes & Hayes 2014) was originally created by M. Joseph Hughes, Oregon State University, and was derived manually from Landsat Operational Land Imager (OLI) scenes. Its purpose was to validate cloud and cloud shadow masking derived from the Spatial Procedures for Automated Removal of Cloud and Shadow (SPARCS) algorithm.

The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center in Sioux Falls, SD developed a cloud validation dataset from 96 unique Landsat 8 images called the “L8 Biome” dataset. These images were selected from various locations around the world, and are evenly divided between eight unique biomes and three different cloud cover categories. The images are curated by biome and cloud cover to reduce bias in any one region or cloud cover density. While these validation images were subjectively designed by a single analyst, they provide useful information for quantifying the accuracy of clouds flagged by various cloud masking algorithms.

The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center in Sioux Falls, SD developed a cloud validation dataset from 48 unique Landsat 8 Collection 2 images, called the “Landsat 8 Collection 2 cloud truth mask validation set”. These images were selected at random from the Landsat 8 archive from various locations around the world. While these validation images were subjectively designed by a single analyst, they provide useful information for quantifying the accuracy of clouds flagged by various cloud masking algorithms.

For the Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 GSFC dataset (Skakun et al. 2020b), ground-based images of the sky were collected from 2017 through 2019 using a smartphone camera with a fisheye lens. These data were collected manually during the Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 overpasses. Reference data were collected for 6 Landsat 8 and 28 Sentinel-2 scenes. The ground-based images were used to assist with manual labelling of clouds in Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 imagery.

To produce the PixBox dataset a trained experienced expert(s) manually labels pixels of an image sensor into a pre-defined detailed set of classes. These are typically different cloud transparencies, cloud shadow, condition of underlying surface (“semi-transparent clouds over snow”, “clouds over bright scattering water”). An average collected dataset includes several 10-thousands of pixels because it has to be representative for all classes, and for various observation and environmental conditions, such as climate zones, sun illumination etc. The PixBox-L8-CMIX dataset is a pixel

collection containing 18,830 pixels manually collected from 11 Landsat 8 Level 1 products. The PixBox-S2-CMIX dataset is a pixel collection containing 17,351 pixels manually collected from 29 Sentinel-2 A & B Level 1C products.

The "S2 Hollstein dataset" is a database of manually labelled Sentinel-2A spectra, which were used in the paper by (Hollstein et al., 2016). The database is currently hosted by the Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) of Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum GFZ. The data is available from the GFZ Git . The collection was done based on the early Sentinel-2 products. The main purpose of the dataset was to be a training dataset for a classifier. Since the Hollstein dataset has been the first Sentinel-2 cloud dataset made freely available, it is the most used Sentinel-2 cloud reference dataset so far.

The Sentinel-2 Cloud Mask Catalogue (Francis et al. 2020) on the other hand is one of the most recent datasets. This dataset comprises cloud masks for 513 1022-by-1022 pixel subscenes, at 20m resolution, sampled random from the 2018 Level-1C Sentinel-2 archive. The design of this dataset follows from some observations about cloud masking: (i) performance over an entire product is highly correlated, thus subscenes provide more value per-pixel than full scenes, (ii) current cloud masking datasets often focus on specific regions, or hand-select the products used, which introduces a bias into the dataset that is not representative of the real-world data, (iii) cloud mask performance appears to be highly correlated to surface type and cloud structure, so testing should include analysis of failure modes in relation to these variables. The data was annotated semi-automatically, using the IRIS toolkit, which allows users to dynamically train a Random Forest (implemented using LightGBM), speeding up annotations by iteratively improving its predictions, but preserving the annotator's ability to make final manual changes when needed. The problem with this dataset is the hidden agenda of usage within the development of the SEnSel algorithm (Francis et al. 2021).

Sentinel-2 reference cloud masks generated by an active learning method (Baetens & Hagolle 2018) provides a reference cloud mask data set for 38 Sentinel-2 scenes. These reference masks have been created with the ALCD tool. They were created to validate the cloud masks generated by the MAJA software (Hagolle et al. 2010).

All presented datasets are based on using the satellite data itself (Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8) to derive the reference. Some use manual classification of single pixels or multiple pixels using polygons, while others use semi-automated classification approaches. Only the dataset created by Skakun et al. 2020b, used ground based sky images to aid the classification of S2 and L8 data. Nevertheless, the reference was created on the satellite data itself.

Reference sources

A good number of studies have been carried out to compare and validate the performance of different cloud masking algorithms, especially for S2 and L8, like Hollstein 2016, Baetens et al. 2019, Skakun et al. 2020a, Wevers et al. 2021 or Francis 2021. These studies have in common, the use of references based on the satellite data itself.

Also using satellite data as a reference source, but those from a different satellite, was done by Frey et al. 2020 for the validation of the MODIS-VIIRS Cloud Mask (MVCM). They used MODIS and Cloud-Aerosol Lidar with Orthogonal Polarization (CALIOP) onboard the Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observation (CALIPSO) satellite from the A-Train. And validated the MVCM against clouds detected by CALIOP.

Besides these studies, other researchers have tried to tackle the question of cloud mask performance using references created by other sources. Especially one study by Letu et al. 2014 is of high significance for the work presented here. They analysed the usability of ground-based sky camera images (based on a professional sky camera system at the Space Information Center (TSIC) of Tokai University Japan) for the validation of medium to low resolution sensors (MODIS, AVHRR) cloud masks. Since the resolution of the sensors was low, the whole field of view (FOV) of the sky camera could be used to calculate a cloud cover percentage and compare to one pixel of the sensors. Since the goal of this exercise is to create a validation source for CMIX, currently focused on high resolution (HR) data, the approach can not be adapted as is, since multiple pixels of the sensors will cover the FOV of the sky camera. Nevertheless, the study gives valuable input for defining requirements.

Another important study for the work presented here was published by Joro et al. 2009. In the study, a ceilometer network over Finland is used to validate the performance of SEVIRI and AVHRR cloud masks. Nevertheless, again this study is using sensors with much lower resolutions and only aiming at analysing the agreement between the ceilometers and a N x N pixel window of the satellite sensors, which is a spatially very rough comparison taking the low resolution of the sensors into account. Additionally, the information of the ceilometer is integrated over a longer period, as is the data scanned by SEVIRI. All of this indicates quite a big uncertainty of the comparability of the two different measurements. The study presents "proportion correct" (PC) for all comparisons, which is the same as the "overall

accuracy” of a confusion matrix. The validation results for PC are always between 0.75 and 0.85, which is quite moderate. This can either be caused by a bad performance of the cloud masking algorithms or the reference is not suitable for the comparison. In the discussion section shortcomings of the approach are addressed, which can be very valuable for this study here.

The study by Ackermann et al 2008 also gives valuable information for the work presented here. Ackermann et al. 2008 have assessed the performance of MODIS cloud mask by using the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) Program Active Remotely Sensed Cloud (ARSCL) product that combines ground-based observations from a micropulse lidar (MPL) and a millimeter-wavelength cloud radar (MMCR) to determine cloud presence and cloud-top heights. A group of 5 x 5 MODIS observations centered on the ARM site was used in the comparison, averaging the final cloud mask confidences.

A further study of publications using other medium to low resolution sensors has been disregarded, since the transferability of findings from these study seems questionable.

2.1.3 Findings from Cloud Mask Intercomparison eXercise (CMIX)

In this section a short summary of the CMIX is given. In addition, the identified shortcomings of existing reference datasets are presented and recommendations for new references are given.

Short summary of the exercise (Wevers et al 2021):

CMIX was a valuable lesson for the participants as well as for the organization team. It was the first exercise of its kind and helped to better understand what is needed to compare and validate different cloud masks. Especially shortcomings and limitations in used reference datasets have been identified, while the exercise still revealed the differences in the compared cloud screening algorithms. Therefore, it helped to identify strengths and weaknesses of single algorithm/method.

Identified shortcomings of the reference datasets:

As results from CMIX-I showed existing validation datasets varied in how a cloud was defined, and it influenced performance of the algorithms. One potential metric to define the cloud would be the cloud optical thickness, for example. However, this poses the questions at which wavelength to be defined. While there was a consensus between algorithms and developers in defining thick non-transparent clouds, there was a disagreement (sometimes by design and depending on the intended applications) in transparent (semi-transparent) clouds, such as cirrus and stratus, and cloud edges. Also, the effect of those clouds can vary with wavelengths, which adds complexity to the analysis.

Recommendations of CMIX for improving reference datasets:

The recommendations for a new CMIX reference dataset are:

- Implementing consistently the cloud definition and adding cloud shadows to the analysis. Recommended practices for labelling clouds shall be developed and implemented for new datasets, whether through visual interpretation or ground measurements or ancillary data (e.g. geostationary satellites). Clouds shadows should be also part of the analysis, since inaccurate cloud mask can lead to substantial artefacts in the downstream products.
- Increasing the number of sites of ground-based imagery of the sky and use them in coordination with Aeronet measurements.
- Acquire multiple datasets over the same area to analyse consistent errors in cloud detection. This would enable temporal metrics to be exploited when assessing the efficiency of cloud masks.

Further recommendations regarding the framework:

- Sample-based approach versus area-based approach, when comparing reference cloud mask with the predicted one. The problem with an area-based approach is that more weights would be given to large clouds (which cover the larger area), whereas smaller clouds might have a small impact on the performance metrics. But sampled based approaches can also miss some specific land cover features, and sometimes do not address the limits of the clouds. Both approaches are therefore necessary.
- Temporal analysis of cloud masks over the same area. Originally planned for CMIX-I, the idea of using temporal metrics was abandoned, since no reference data (except GSFC which were assisted with sky imagery and Aeronet measurements) was available for these purposes. Nevertheless, undetected clouds add noise on time series, therefore it is possible to evaluate the noise on time series, and compute the contribution of different cloud masks to this noise.
- Application-based approach to cloud validation. One way to analyse efficiency of the cloud/shadow masks is to “validate” them indirectly within the downstream products. An example can include a generic land cover mapping workflow, when the same set of satellite data will be processed by various cloud detection algorithms and used an input to the classification algorithm. The derived land cover maps will be validated using the same validation data and inter-compared.

Implications for this study:

One recommendation of the CMIX was the increase of ground-based imagery of the sky sites, therefore this study is important to proof the fitness for purpose. Nevertheless, a network of sky cameras can only address some of the requirements formulated and needs to be combined with other approaches to create complementing reference datasets to fulfil all requirements.

2.1.4 Requirements depending on applications

In meteorology, a cloud is a mass of water drops or ice crystals suspended in the atmosphere. Clouds form when water condenses in the sky. The condensation lets us see the water vapor. There are many different types of clouds. (Hitt 2011).

Clouds are divided into five physical forms which can be further divided or classified into altitude levels to derive ten basic genera. The main representative cloud types for each of these forms are stratus, cirrus, stratocumulus, cumulus, and cumulonimbus. Low-level clouds do not have any altitude-related prefixes. However mid-level stratiform and stratocumuliform types are given the prefix alto- while high-level variants of these same two forms carry the prefix cirro-. Genus types with sufficient vertical extent to occupy more than one level do not carry any altitude related prefixes.

What is lacking from this nomenclature is the a) density of water droplets and/or ice crystals forming the clouds, b) the composition of the cloud (water droplets and/or ice crystals) and c) temperature (only partially related to the cloud types). All factors have a strong influence on emission and scattering of electromagnetic (EM) radiation by the atmosphere and surface. Especially the composition and temperature lead to differences in the visibility/influence of clouds in different ranges of the EM spectrum. But the dependency between spectral wavelength and cloud properties is of great importance for the definition of clouds for satellite-based cloud detection as well as for creating a useful validation reference. Therefore, a first requirement of a good reference dataset would be to include information on the wavelength for which the cloud is an obstruction (“visible”).

The requirements of a cloud mask and thus for a reference dataset, do not only depend on the physical definition of a cloud, but also on the subsequent application. These requirements arise from the fact that on the one side no cloud mask can be 100% correct, and on the other side the threshold for a combination of water droplets and/or ice crystals to be recognised as a cloud vary between different application. In general applications, and thus also the cloud masking algorithms, can be categorized into three major classes: cloud conservative and non-cloud conservative and balanced. Non-cloud conservative approaches are mostly needed for applications that do not allow cloud contamination (e.g. the remote sensing of land, sea-, and ice surface temperatures, of vegetation biophysical variables, of total column water

vapor or of aerosol optical properties), while cloud conservative approaches are mostly needed for cloud remote sensing applications. Depending on the application and sensor, a commission error can be rated as less problematic, for example due to the high repetition cycle of Sentinel-2. For these cases it might be a big issue, if the error is systematic (Wevers et al 2021).

2.1.4.1 Applications with non-cloud conservative needs

Applications with non-cloud conservative needs would prefer the loss of some non-cloud observations instead of contamination of any cloud in the measurement. One of the strictest applications in this sense is AOD retrieval, since any cloud will lead to wrong estimates. Nevertheless, any obstruction of the signal, caused by aerosols is a wanted measurement for AOD retrieval, which in case of other applications might also be considered as unwanted. Therefore, the term non-cloud and not clear was chosen. This fact leads to the requirement for the reference data to distinguish between clouds and aerosols.

Other applications non-cloud conservative needs are more capable of allowing a certain amount of residual cloud contamination. Especially applications using multitemporal inputs from sensors like S2 MSI with high repeat cycles are often capable of statistically removing these contaminations from the time series. Nevertheless, systematic, and close to systematic errors in cloud flagging will lead to problems. This leads to the next three requirements for a good reference dataset, 1) to provide multitemporal observations for the same location, 2) to provide information at the location of known problematic features in cloud masking for most sensors, like bright targets (beaches, salt lakes, exposed bright bedrock), urban areas and snow, and 3) to provide information well distributed over all land cover types. Some confusions in cloud detection can also be caused by bright (mostly inland) waters (high sediment load, coccolithophores bloom, high chlorophyll content). This leads to the next requirement for a good reference dataset, to provide information well distributed over different types of water surfaces. This requirement will be very hard to achieve for a sky camera-based reference dataset, since placing sensors on water surfaces might be close to impossible. Since a mobile location will lead to unequal observations, the location of the sky camera must be stable and thus cannot be floating. This means, only locations close to water surfaces, or on fixed platforms on water surfaces are feasible. This also means no open ocean references can be produced with this approach.

2.1.4.2 Applications with cloud conservative needs

Cloud conservative applications are those interested in clouds itself. This is mainly limited to cloud remote sensing. For cloud conservative approaches, any non-cloud pixels can be interpreted as a contamination. This includes clear surface as well as aerosols. The later again leads to the requirement for the reference data to distinguish between clouds and aerosols, to be able to test any cloud masking algorithm for its capability to differentiate or at least to evaluate its behaviour regarding aerosols. Again, systematic false detections are a big issue for cloud conservative approaches and lead to the requirements already defined in the section above.

2.1.4.3 Applications with balanced needs

Balanced needs represent the ideal that all cloud screening algorithms should strive for. Nevertheless, a balanced behaviour can only satisfy the need of the two prior presented, if close to 100% accuracy is achieved. Therefore, applications with balanced needs are those who can deal with a certain amount of cloud residuals as well as loss of non-cloud measurements. These needs do not lead to any further requirements besides those presented above.

2.2 Measurement requirements

In the previous section a few requirements in the reference data have been formulated using the needs of different types of applications. These requirements can be used to define requirements for the measurements of a ground based sky camera. The identified requirements were:

- include information on the wavelength for which the cloud is an obstruction (“visible”)
- distinguish between clouds and aerosols
- provide multitemporal observations for the same location
- provide information at the location of known problematic features
- provide information well distributed over all land cover types
- provide information well distributed over different types of water surfaces

These requirements can be used to define temporal, spatial and spectral requirements for the measurements and evaluate how these can be fulfilled by a ground-based sky camera system.

2.2.1 Temporal requirements

There are two requirements that need to be addressed here. First the frequency in which the reference is created, and second availability of the final reference for further analysis.

2.2.1.1 Monitoring frequencies

The ideal monitoring frequency for a reference dataset would be for every acquisition any remote sensing sensor acquires. The delay between the ground image and satellite acquisition should be not more than 1 minute.

Nearly all reference datasets/methods presented in the previous chapters are not able to fulfil this requirement, since only one or a few acquisitions in time over one site have been captured. The ground-based sky camera approach is the only method fulfilling this requirement, besides lidar or radar measurements, for which no openly available reference dataset is existing.

2.2.1.2 Data availability for further analysis

The ideal availability of the reference dataset after acquisition would be near real-time (NRT), to allow constant evaluation of cloud masking quality. Nevertheless, a weekly or monthly availability would still be superior to any other dataset yet produced. Especially if continuously provided, this kind of dataset would be unique.

2.2.2 Spatial requirements

Following the requirements for a good reference dataset formulated by Congalton (1991) and Congalton and Green (2019) and keeping in mind that the globally occurring “phenomenon” of clouds should be represented properly, the following three spatial requirements for a reference measurement need to be addressed: data resolution, sampling area size and global distribution.

2.2.2.1 Sampling unit - data resolution

Ideally the resolution of the reference dataset matches the resolution of the cloud mask that is validated. In the case of different satellite based earth observation sensors this leads to multiple resolution. Nevertheless, a higher to equal resolution reference compared to the validated mask should be preferred over lower resolution.

2.2.2.2 Geometric accuracy - comparability of the validated object

Ideally the geometric accuracy is below pixel resolution. Most existing reference datasets are generated using the satellite data itself. In these cases, the geometric accuracy can be neglected since reference and validated product share the same source.

For ground-based sky camera observations this poses quite a big challenge, since the sensor on ground, has a completely different viewing geometry compared to the space borne sensor, even if lens distortion is corrected. Additionally, the observed object is placed between the validation source (satellite-based CM) and the reference (sky camera based CM reference), and the validated object is three dimensional, leading to the fact that the satellite sensor potentially sees a complete different part of the validated object compared to the reference. Or in other words, it is possible that the satellite sensor observes the visible ground, while the ground-based reference identifies a cloud, and vice versa.

2.2.2.3 Sample size

The answer for a required samples size cannot be easily answered. If we assume that we have only two classes, cloud and non-cloud we expect a bimodal distribution. Calculating the sample size for bimodal distributions dependent on two factors:

- the level of acceptable error that can be accepted
- the desired level of confidence

There are multiple publications available dealing with good sample size selection for bimodal distributions (Congalton & Green 2019). Some provide look-up table like Cochran, 1977 or Ginevan, 1979. While bimodal distribution potentially is the false estimation when validating cloud masks, we will still follow this path shortly analyse based on a bimodal distribution.

It is already tricky to define the number of assessment judgements or population. For a Sentinel- 2 for example this would be every uniquely sensed pixel from the complete time series. Or if a certain processing baseline of the L2A cloud screening needs to be assessed. All uniquely sensed pixels within the time period of this processing baseline. But this population is hard to determine. If we take 1,489,400,000,000,000 m² of global land mass as a reference, we will end up with approx. 14,894,000,000,000,000 S2 10m pixels over land, which might be an underestimation, since a lot of coastal areas are covered by S2 including the ocean areas. Then each pixel is revisited between multiple times daily to every 5 days, depending on latitude. Let's take the 5 days repetition as an example. This leads to 73 observations per year. 14,894,000,000,000,000 times 37 leads to 1,087,262,000,000,000,000. We will use this number to predict some sample sizes using different margin of errors and confidence levels. The response distribution is defined to be 50%. So equally distributed between cloud and non-cloud, which might be wrong since the mean global cloud cover is 66%. Nevertheless, this also accounts for sea surfaces. Therefore, 50% is kept here.

Table 1: Potential sample sizes for one year of Sentinel-2 acquisitions

Population	Margin of error	Confidence level	Sample size
1.08726E+18	5%	95%	358
1.08726E+18	5%	99%	664
1.08726E+18	1%	95%	9604
1.08726E+18	1%	99%	16588
1.08726E+18	0.5%	99%	66349

Let's further follow the road of a bimodal distribution and see what this implies for a sky camera network to produce these kinds of samples. If the classification of the sky camera data works flawless and the geometric matching is 100% correct. There might be a good chance 500x500 pixel windows to be provided as a reference by the sky camera. This will lead to 250,000 reference samples. Thus, one acquisition alone would be statistically sound as a reference, if cloud and non-cloud is represented 50% each. Nevertheless, this might not be true, since all samples would be spatially correlated and do not reflect the global distribution of clouds, differences in cloud types and differences in surfaces, influencing semi-transparent clouds.

Assuming only a 3x3 pixel window would define the reference of a single camera, a sample size of 66349 can be created by nearly 101 sky cameras, since one camera creates 9 references per overpass. With 73 overpasses per year, we get 657 references for a single sky camera. 101 cameras will then produce 66357 references. Aiming at lower error and confidence levels, the reference might already be provided by a single sky camera station. But again, this will not reflect the global distribution of clouds, nor the influence of different surface types.

Now coming back to the global cloud distribution and the variety of surface types and its influence semi-transparent clouds, leads to the conclusion that there is no single class cloud, but clouds are very variable and in a lot of cases intermingled with underlying surfaces. Additionally, they very often don't have sharp borders. This all leads to the conclusion that there can't be a bimodal distribution between non-cloud and cloud since cloud is split into n classes of cloud. With n not being easy to determine. This would further increase the number of required samples.

However, the theoretical calculations for a bimodal distribution and further thoughts on potentially created samples per sky camera show that already a few sky cameras can create a valuable reference dataset with a good confidence and error level. Increase in sky cameras would lead to an increase in spatial distribution, which will be address hereafter.

2.2.2.4 Global site distribution

Approximately 66% of all global surfaces are covered by clouds. Figure 1 illustrates the average cloud occurrence between 2000 and 2014. While some areas are very rarely covered by clouds some areas have cloud occurrences above 75%, giving even satellites with high repetition times only a slight chance to measure a clear surface spectrum.

Figure 1: Global mean annual cloud occurrence map (Wilson, A. M., Jetz, W [2016])

This global distribution of cloud occurrences and the globally greatly varying land surfaces, show the need of a globally well distributed dataset. Even areas with little to no cloud occurrence need to be represented, since these areas often include problematic surfaces like salt.

2.2.3 Thematic requirements

Congalton (1991) stated that the significance of any assessment is depending on the correctness of the reference. Each collection method adds a certain bias to the reference. This leads to the requirements that the bias needs to be known and kept as low as possible. As described in section 2.2.2.2 there is quite some bias introduced by the differences in geometries. These differences will automatically lead to thematic differences. If this introduced bias cannot be quantified, this will reduce the significance of the dataset.

Furthermore, classifying the sky camera pixels into cloud/non-cloud classes again introduces a certain amount of bias. Manual classification will include a bias introduced by the interpreter. This bias can be determined using a great number of different interpreters as a reference. An automatic classification introduces even more unknown bias, since the classifier first has to be trained, which again needs a biased expert.

2.2.4 Spectral requirements

Ideally the reference is created using the exact same spectral properties compared to the validated satellite sensor.

2.3 Analysis requirements

The overarching requirement for a quality assessment analysis of satellite cloud masks is the ability to unravel systematic and non-systematic errors in classification.

There are two factors that have a strong influence on the ability of the analysis to fulfil the above stated requirement, the quality of the reference data, and the analysis method used for the assessment. Thus we will have a closer look on these two factors and how they relate to the sky camera approach.

2.3.1 Quality of the reference dataset

The quality of the reference data was already detailed in section 2.2. Nevertheless, some details regarding the sky camera approach need to be evaluated.

If the sky cameras operate on a continuous basis and thus provide a continuously growing validation source for a variety of satellite sensors, the only way to achieve this is through automatic classification of the sky camera (SC) data. But automatic classification will always introduce a higher error compared to manual classification. Therefore, the introduced error somehow needs to be quantified and provided with the reference data.

Besides the classification accuracy influencing the reference data quality, the used data (SC images) itself might introduce some sort of error. During experimental operation phase of the sky cameras issues regarding the geometric agreement between clouds in the SCs and the satellite images due to viewing geometry differences have been discovered. Details are given in the "Operations and Validation Report". How to circumvent these issues needs to be evaluated in a potential next phase of the project.

2.3.2 Quantitative versus qualitative analysis

When assessing thematic accuracies quantitatively the common practice is to use confusion matrices, as already presented in section 2.1.1. Nevertheless, not all classification errors that occur in a cloud mask can easily be identified by a quantitative analysis. Therefore, qualitative analysis is another good approach to detect more semi-systematic errors. This means errors that always occur at certain feature, but not always over the same target. Qualitative analysis is also the only method that can give a first indication for systematic errors and detect features that can cause these errors. Quantitative analysis can then be used to collect samples for these features and quantify the occurrence.

The sky camera approach mainly delivers a quantitative reference that can be used for a quantitative analysis. If the sky camera site is not placed close to a feature that potentially can cause systematic false detections, the method cannot be used to determine these types of errors. Nevertheless, the SC images itself can be very valuable when manual interpreting satellite data and thus can aid a qualitative analysis.

2.4 Instrumentation state of the art

This analysis was quite complicated since there are a great many instruments and networks operational. Probably only a small fraction of it is publicly documented/available or documented in English language. Furthermore understanding of dependencies between networks and fundings, as well as status of operability is not always clear and easy to understand and to evaluate. Therefore, this section only provides a shallow overview of existing networks and instrumentations used for cloud monitoring. A deeper knowledge of those networks would be required to make a significant analysis. A lot of these methods are also not comparable with sky cameras, for example if having a completely different measurement resolution.

It is also important to note that there are multiple other atmospheric monitoring networks that don't provide information on clouds like Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change (NDACC) for example. Some of the data of these networks might be a proxy for cloud presence, but don't provide specific information of cloud occurrence.

2.4.1 Overview of monitoring networks

2.4.1.1 Cloudnet

“The aim of Cloudnet is to provide a systematic evaluation of clouds in forecast models. Clouds and their associated microphysical processes strongly regulate radiative transfer and the hydrological cycle, and are often themselves important for end users of weather forecasts, who may be interested not only in cloud cover, but in other variables determined by cloud properties, such as surface precipitation, temperatures, or shortwave/ultraviolet radiation. In order to provide these variables, accurate prediction of the vertical and horizontal distribution of cloud ice and liquid water contents is necessary.”

CLU provides vertical profiles of cloud and turbulent properties at high temporal and spatial resolution from a network of ground-based stations using the Cloudnet processing suite. Major objectives also include the development and validation of new synergetic remote sensing algorithms, and the continuous evaluation of the representation of clouds and other atmospheric parameters in climate and weather forecast models.

Cloudnet provides multiple cloud/aerosol related parameters for approx. 18 stations across Europe (see Figure 2), which are not all operational. The data is based on different instruments and combination of these (e.g. lidar and radar).

Figure 2: Example of data available from Cloudnet

Cloudnet is also one key element of ACTRIS research infrastructure, which will be described in the next section. ACTRIS Data Centre node for cloud profiling (CLU) utilizes Cloudnet ecosystem to serve official ACTRIS cloud remote sensing products through the ACTRIS data portal.

2.4.1.2 ACTRIS network – Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure

European Research Infrastructure for the observation of Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases, ACTRIS.

ACTRIS – Aerosols, Clouds, and Trace Gases - is the pan-European RI that consolidates activities amongst European partners for observations of aerosols, clouds, and trace gases and for understanding of the related atmospheric processes, to provide RI services to wide user groups. ACTRIS is composed of 9 connected elements: distributed National Facilities (observation platforms and exploratory platforms) both in Europe and globally, and 8 Central Facilities (Head Office, Data Centre and 6 Topical Centres). ACTRIS provides access to its facilities, open-access data, measurement support, instrument calibration and development, and training to various user groups.

Figure 3 shows the location of the ACTRIS funded sites.

Figure 3: ACTRIS funded sites

2.4.1.3 Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) - cloud mode observations

The Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) is a ground-based network that is designed to measure microphysical and optical properties of aerosols. AERONET is composed of Sun/sky radiometers with a 1.2° field-of-view (FOV) that measure radiance at wavelengths of 440, 675, 870, and 1020 nm. Direct Sun measurements are mainly used to screen out clouds and to retrieve aerosol optical depth, while sky radiance measurements are mainly used to retrieve aerosol microphysical and optical properties such as aerosol size distribution, phase function, and single scattering albedo. AERONET aerosol retrievals, available at more than 250 sites, have been extensively used to quantify aerosol direct and indirect effects, validate satellite aerosol retrievals, and develop aerosol forecast models.

When clouds completely block the Sun, direct Sun and sky measurements are not appropriate for retrieving aerosol optical properties. In these situations, the radiometer was placed into sleep mode. As a result, it was propose to use some of this idle time to observe clouds. This new mode for monitoring clouds is called “cloud mode.” In cloud mode, AERONET radiometers point directly up (i.e., zenith) and perform 10 zenith radiance measurements at 9 s intervals for each wavelength, which are obtained by successively rotating an interference filter in front of the detector.

2.4.1.4 Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) Program

The Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) user facility is a multi-laboratory, U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) scientific user facility, and a key contributor to national and international climate research efforts.

ARM data are currently collected from three atmospheric observatories—Southern Great Plains, North Slope of Alaska, and Eastern North Atlantic—that represent the broad range of climate conditions around the world, as well as from the three ARM mobile facilities and ARM aerial facilities. Data from these atmospheric observatories, as well as from past research campaigns and the former Tropical Western Pacific observatory, are available at no charge through the ARM Data Center via Data Discovery.

Nine DOE national laboratories share the responsibility of managing and operating ARM. Along with these laboratories, several constituent groups help provide scientific guidance and develop ARM priorities. ARM also collaborates with many national and international partners.

ARM has provided the world's atmospheric scientists with continuous observations of cloud and aerosol properties and their impacts on the Earth's energy balance for almost 30 years.

2.4.2 Overview of ground-based cloud monitoring instruments

A variety of instruments is used for ground-based cloud monitoring. The set of instruments include Radar, Lidar, Microwave radiometers as well as sky cameras operated in multiple wavelengths. All instruments are either operated stand-alone or in a combined setup. In the following sections a brief overview of each instrument group is given. Examples are mostly taken from ARM.

2.4.2.1 Radar

Radar is mainly used to monitor cloud properties and evolution. Monitored properties are for example cloud boundaries (top and bottom), and microphysical properties like cloud particle size and mass content. (Clothiaux et al., 2000)

Cloud radars are operated in different bands, spanning from Ka-band over W-band to X-band. Longer wavelengths are less affected by big particles like drizzle or rain, while shorter wavelengths are more sensitive to very small particles. It is also important to note that the radar signal can be heavily affected by insects or even birds. (Khandwalla et al., 2002)

Below is a list of some operationally used radar instruments:

- University of Massachusetts cloud profiling radar system
 - The Cloud Profiling Radar System (CPRS) is a single antenna, two frequency (33 GHz and 95 GHz) polarimetric radar operated by the University of Massachusetts (UMASS). This system is capable of making four dimensional Doppler and polarimetric measurements of clouds.
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/umasscprs>
- Ka-Band Scanning ARM Cloud Radar (KASACR)
 - Rather than focusing on plan position indicator, or PPI, scans, the KASACR uses range height indicator, or RHI, scans at numerous azimuths to obtain cloud volume data.
 - Instrument shown in Figure 4.
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/kasacr>
- WACR W-Band (95 GHz) ARM Cloud Radar
 - The W-band ARM Cloud Radar (WACR) systems are zenith-pointing Doppler radars that probe the extent and composition of clouds at 95.04 GHz. The main purpose of this radar is to determine cloud boundaries (e.g., cloud bottoms and tops).
 - Instrument shown in Figure 5
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/wacr>
- WSACR W-band Scanning ARM Cloud Radar
 - Measurements collected with the W-SACR are copolar and cross-polar radar reflectivity, Doppler velocity, spectra width and spectra when not scanning, and linear depolarization ration.
 - Instrument shown in Figure 6. Figure 5
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/wsacr>
- XSACR X-Band Scanning ARM Cloud Radar
 - Beamwidth for the X-band is approximately 1 degree
 - Rather than focusing on plan position indicator, or PPI, scans, the XSACR uses range height indicator, or RHI, scans at numerous azimuths to obtain cloud volume data.
 - Instrument shown in Figure 7. Figure 5
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/xsacr>

Figure 4: Ka-Band Scanning ARM Cloud Radar

Figure 5: W-band (95 GHz) ARM Cloud Radar

Figure 6: W-band Scanning ARM Cloud Radar

Figure 7: X-band Scanning ARM Cloud Radar

2.4.2.2 Lidar

Lidars have been proven useful for classification of cloud types (i.e., cumuli versus cirrus). Cloud boundaries can be retrieved from a ground-based lidar operating at a visible and/or near-infrared band. Cloud-base height can be identified by the time difference between the transmittance of the laser pulse to the sky and the detection of the backscattered light by the telescope. The laser beam is always attenuated when it penetrates through the clouds. However, when a powerful laser (e.g., Nd:YAG laser with high energy per pulse) is used, cloud tops can be retrieved too. Another physical parameter that can be retrieved is the cloud phase.

Nevertheless, conventional lidar systems, like the ARM instruments Doppler lidar (DL), High-spectral-resolution lidar (HSRL), The micropulse lidar (MPL), or Raman lidar (RL) are usually only used to measure atmospheric properties like aerosol scattering, moisture or temperature.

2.4.2.3 Ceilometer

A ceilometer in principle is a low power lidar with a vertical pointing laser. A laser ceilometer consists of a vertically pointing laser and a receiver in the same location. A laser pulse with a duration on the order of nanoseconds is sent through the atmosphere. As the beam travels through the atmosphere, tiny fractions of the light are scattered by aerosols. Generally, the size of the particles in question are similar in size to the wavelength of the laser.

Examples for ceilometers are:

- Belfort Laser Ceilometer

- The Belfort laser ceilometer (BLC) Model 7013C field unit is a self-contained, ground-based, optical, active remote-sensing instrument with the ability to detect and process several cloud-related parameters. These parameters include cloud height, extinction coefficient, cloud layers, and time/date reference information. The ceilometer system detects clouds by transmitting pulses of infrared light vertically into the atmosphere. The receiver telescope detects scattered light from clouds and precipitation.
- Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/blc>
- CEIL
 - The ceilometer (CEIL) is a remote-sensing instrument that measures cloud height, vertical visibility, and potential backscatter signals by aerosols. It detects up to three cloud layers simultaneously. Operating through a maximum vertical range of 7700 m, the CEIL transmits near-infrared pulses of light and the receiver detects the light scattered back by clouds and precipitation.
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/ceil>
- RAP - Raymetrics Aerosol Profiles
 - RAP (Raymetrics' Aerosol Profiler), is a recently developed elastic backscatter mini-LiDAR. It is here to close the gap between ceilometers and high energy backscatter lidars. All QA and QC hardware and software tools based on ACTRIS requirements are included on basic configuration.
 - The system is suitable for cloud detection, tropospheric aerosol layers detection (i.e desert dust, biomass burning plumes, volcanic ash), PBL height studies. It delivers atmospheric backscatter aerosol profiles in the NIR with high raw spatial and temporal resolution 3.75m, <20sec, respectively. The effective range extends from full overlap (<200m) up to 15km.
 - Data will be available through BAQUNIN: <https://www.baqunin.eu/products/>

2.4.2.4 Sky cameras

- Mobotix Q24
 - Hemispheric low-cost sky camera, model Mobotix Q24, placed on the rooftop of the Solar Energy Research Center (CIESOL) at the University of Almería, Spain
 - The images produced are high resolution from a fully digital color CMOS (2048 x 1536 pixels).
 - Instrument shown in Figure 8
- ARM Stereo Cameras
 - STEREOCAM consists of three pairs of stereo camera setups that aim to provide synchronized and stereo calibrated time series of images that can be used for 3D cloud mask reconstruction. Each camera pair is positioned at approximately 120 degrees from the other pair, with a 17°-19° pitch angle from the ground, and at 5-6 km distance from the ARM Southern Great Plains observatory to cover the region from northeast, northwest, and southern views. Images from both cameras of the same stereo setup can be paired together to obtain 3D reconstruction by triangulation. 3D reconstructions from the ring of three stereo pairs can be combined together to generate a 3D mask from surrounding views.
 - Measurements:
 - Images of Clouds
 - Surface condition
 - Instrument shown in Figure 9
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/stereocam>

- ARM Whole Sky Imager (WSI)
 - The whole-sky imager (WSI) is an automated imager used for assessing and documenting cloud fields and cloud field dynamics. The WSI is a ground-based electronic imaging system that monitors the upper hemisphere. It is a passive, i.e., non-emissive, system that acquires images of the sky dome through three spectral filters (neutral, red, and blue).
 - From these sky images, we can assess the presence, distribution, shape, and radiance of clouds over the entire sky using automated cloud decision algorithms and related processing. The current WSI model (EO System 6) is capable of image acquisition under daylight, moonlight, and starlight conditions.
 - Measurements:
 - Cloud fraction
 - Instrument shown in Figure 10.
 - Data is available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/wsi>

- ARM Total-Sky Imager (TSI)
 - The total sky imager (TSI) measures the fraction of the sky view covered by clouds.
 - It provides time series of hemispheric sky images during daylight hours and retrievals of fractional sky cover for periods when the solar elevation is greater than 10 degrees. To view current sky cover retrievals at the ARM sites, see the TSI most recent sky images.
 - Measurements:
 - Cloud fraction
 - Instrument is shown in Figure 11.
 - Data available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/tsi>

- ARM Infra-Red Sky Imager (IRSI)
 - The infrared sky imager (IRSI) measures cloud fraction and precipitable water vapor. The IRSI captures hemispheric sky images and provide time series retrievals of fractional sky cover during both day and night. The instrument provides diurnal sky imagery in the mid-infrared atmospheric window and imagery during daylight hours in the visible wavelengths for cloud retrievals. The software automatically identifies cloudy and clear regions and calculates fractional sky cover.
 - Measurements:
 - Atmospheric moisture
 - Cloud base height
 - Cloud fraction
 - Longwave narrowband brightness temperature
 - Precipitable water
 - Instrument is shown in Figure 12.
 - Data available through ARM: <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/instruments/irsi>

- All-Sky Imager developed by Atmospheric Physics Group (GFAT)
 - The All-Sky Imager was developed by GFAT to provide images of the whole sky dome in daytime for the purpose of cloud characterization, and it is used for research associated with radiative transfer in the atmosphere
 - The All-Sky Imager is a custom adaptation of a scientific CCD camera. The principal modifications are the lens, the environmental housing, and the solar-shadow system.
 - Instrument is shown in Figure 13.
 - Instrument described in: Cazorla, A.; Olmo, F.J.; Alados-Arboledas, L. Development of a sky imager for cloud cover assessment. J. Opt. Soc. Am. A 2008, 25, 29–39.

- whole-sky infrared cloud-measuring system (WSIRCMS) developed by Sun et al (2011)

- The WSIRCMS and ceilometer CL51 were installed with a distance of 10 m between them on the rooftop of the Yangjiang observing station (21°50'N, 111°58'E; and 89.9 m above mean sea level).
- The WSIRCMS is a ground-based passive sensor that uses an uncooled microbolometer detector array to measure downwelling atmospheric radiance in the 8–14- μ m wavelength bands. It provides a way to obtain cloud distribution, calculate cloud amount, and estimate CBH, and to classify cloud types every 15 min with no difference in sensitivity during day and night for elevation angles greater than 15°. The primary WSIRCMS components are an optical detector, environmental parameter sensors, controller, power, and terminal unit. The optical detector is an uncooled microbolometer array containing 320 \times 240 pixels. A whole-sky image is obtained under the control of the scan servo system after combining zenith image and other images at eight different orientations. The whole-sky image has a resolution of 650 \times 650 pixels.
- Development documented in: Xuejin, Sun & Liu, Lei & Zhao, Shijun. (2011). Whole Sky Infrared Remote Sensing of Cloud. *Procedia Earth and Planetary Science*. 2. 278-283. 10.1016/j.proeps.2011.09.044.
- SOLMIRUS - All Sky Infrared Visible Analyzer (ASIVA)
 - The Solmirus All Sky Infrared Visible Analyzer (ASIVA) is a multi-purpose visible and infrared sky imaging and analysis instrument designed to operate autonomously or as a component in an instrument cluster. Its utility ranges from astronomy to a variety of meteorological applications. Available data products include the following:
 - Cloud/No Cloud Reporting
 - Cloud Cover and Height Determination
 - Photometric Quality Assessment
 - Sky Opacity/Transmission Determination
 - Visible/IR Image Correlation and Integration
 - Water Vapor and Ozone determination
 - Sky/Cloud Temperature (brightness and color)
 - Measurements All-Sky (180 degree field-of-view)
 - Radiometric Maps and Analysis
 - Instrument is shown in Figure 14.
 - Description of the instrument is available from SOLMIRUS through: http://www.solmirus.com/files/ASIVA_Instrument_Description_6_21_10.pdf

Figure 8: Mobotix Q24

Figure 9: ARM Stereo Cameras for cloud

Figure 10: Whole-Sky imager

Figure 11: Total Sky Imager

Figure 12: Infrared Sky Imager

Figure 13: All-Sky Imager developed by Atmospheric Physics Group

Figure 14: SOLMIRUS - ASIVA

3. Evaluation of requirements

In section 0 the requirements for validation, measurement and analysis have been presented. In this section it will be evaluated if and how the sky camera approach can meet these requirements. The main focus of the evaluation is based on the measurement requirements since these already consider the validation requirements.

Requirements for the following domains have been identified:

- Monitoring frequency
 - The ideal monitoring frequency for a reference dataset would be for every acquisition any remote sensing sensor acquires. The delay between the ground image and satellite acquisition should be not more than 1 minute.
- Data availability
 - best near real-time (NRT), or at least weekly or monthly
- Sampling unit
 - Ideally the resolution of the reference dataset matches the resolution of the cloud mask that is validated
- Geometric accuracy
 - Ideally the geometric accuracy is below pixel resolution.
- Global site distribution
 - Cloud mask validation poses a need of a globally well distributed dataset
- Thematic accuracy
 - The bias needs to be known and kept as low as possible
- Spectral accuracy
 - The reference is ideally created using the exact same spectral properties compared to the validated satellite sensor.
- Analysis requirements
 - Ability to unravel systematic and non-systematic errors in classification.
- Quality of reference data
 - As listed in the above bullet points
 - Introduced error somehow needs to be quantified and provided with the reference data.

The requirements in the first three domains can be easily achieved by the sky camera approach. Nevertheless, geometric accuracy poses quite an issue as documented in the “Operations and Validation Report” (D2), due to differences in observation geometries. A final evaluation can not be done at this point since the development of algorithms has not matured so far and needs further assessment and development. Since the goal of the project and this document is to produce a road map for upscaling, the requirements of a globally well distributed network can not be reached yet. Nevertheless, UoM and NASA have extended the network already to additionally four other sky camera sites, now consisting of six sites:

- GSFC, Greenbelt, Maryland, USA
- Wisconsin, USA
- Sapienza University, Rome, Italy
- Valencia University, Valencia, Spain
- Sao Paulo University, Sao Paulo, Brazil
- Antarctica¹

The requirements on thematic accuracy depend mostly on the accuracy of the automated SC classification. As shown in the “Operations and Validation Report” (D2) the development of a random forest (RF) classifier was already able to achieve quite good results. More R&D is needed to improve the classification.

The requirements for spectral accuracy cannot be met with the SC approach, since the SCs are bound to the spectral information of the low-cost raspberry PI camera.

¹ <https://geog.umd.edu/feature/umd-skycam-project-deploys-sky-imagers-antarctica>

The analysis requirement could be matched partially. Non-systematic errors can be easily quantified by the SC methods. The detection and quantification of systematic errors depends on the location of the SC sites and the surface features provoking these errors.

The requirement on the quality of the dataset is closely tied to the thematic accuracy. It is important that the errors are quantified and provided with the reference data. To achieve this, further developments are needed.

4. Summary of findings from D2 (Operations and Validation Report)

The results from the experimental operations had shown that the sky camera (SC) data provide an interesting and valuable reference source for evaluation of satellite cloud masks. The strength of the data is the constant acquisition (leading to a dataset with a high temporal resolution), quite high classification accuracy that could be achieved by the random forest classifier, and the comparable low costs for the instrument.

While the validation or better intercomparison results had shown a quite good agreement between the SC classification and the satellite (S2 & L8) cloud masks, the study had also revealed geometric issues that can lead to incomparability between SC and sat data. Further studies are needed to analyse if these issues/disagreements can be circumvented/corrected.

5. Roadmap

The development of a Roadmap for Upscaling requires consideration of all experience and know-how gained during the implementation and experimental operation phase, as documented in the Operations and Validation Report (D2).

The experimental operation has shown that the currently implemented sky camera approach has not yet reached a maturity level that allows for a direct upscaling to a global network. Further R&D is needed to analyse methods to mature the approach. The scope of WP 2185 had not envisaged the development of sky camera pre-processing, since the existence (provision by University of Maryland) of these algorithms was expected at the beginning of the project. Exchange with University of Maryland (UoM) had shown that developments of these algorithms might not be done within a short future. Thus, further developments of own SC pre-processing methods, as already started within WP 2185, should be incorporated into the road map. After further R&D, as well as experimental operation, the performance and suitability of the SC approach needs to be evaluated again. Furthermore, some of the assessments which had been planned for the WP originally and which could not be executed due to missing algorithms need to be conducted, e.g. such as the cloud height comparison between RAP and sky camera estimates.

Despite some setbacks and reaching a less maturity level as expected, the results have shown that the SC approach can provide valuable information for satellite-based cloud mask validation. In addition, UoM and NASA had already moved forward and started extending their network as described in the previous section. While two of these sites are based on European ground and maintained by European entities, the data acquisition and processing is done in the US. Therefore, it is crucial to the European RS community to keep up with the development and become part of such a global network, instead of relying on developments driven by the US. This also means that sky cameras need to be acquired and operated by European entities.

Taking all the above-described experiences into account, a roadmap with four phases has been developed. The goal of each phase is described in the next section.

5.1 Development phases

The roadmap envisages four phases. In the first phase a higher level of maturity of the SC approach needs to be reached and proven. The goal of the second phase is to initiate European self-sufficiency in operating a sky camera site, including raw data processing. This will then be the basis for the third phase of a European roll out. The goal of this phase is to establish approx. 10 European sites. While the fourth and final phase will be the global roll out. Each phase consists of technical tasks and a management task, that also includes outreach and communication. At the end of each phase a go-or-no-go decision needs to be made. For each phase a duration of approx. two years is estimated. The duration for each phase can only be estimated and needs to be adjusted according to progress and outcomes of each phase.

5.1.1 Phase 1: Obtaining level of maturity

Technical tasks

The key technical task of phase 1 will focus on R&D. This includes, finding a solution for the geometry issue, research on proper rectifying algorithms to correct for lens distortion, more research on SC image classification to train a better classifier, find a better solution to treat sun interferences in the SC images, and to test or even develop an algorithm for stereo SC based cloud height estimation, and finally to compare SC based cloud bottom heights with RAP cloud bottom heights. These R&D tasks will be accompanied by continued experimental operation and validation. This part of the R&D activity should finally deliver a proof of concept and show a level of maturity to allow for further extension of the network.

The second part of the R&D task will focus on transferring the current mixture of cloud- and local desktop-based system to a completely cloud-based system. This task will prepare for a sufficient way of processing SC and satellite data and the final data provision to the users. It also should provide a good solution for the users to bring their own data for validation. In the end the R&D activity should lead to a concept for a cloud mask validation system.

Management

Management in this phase should focus on fostering the good engagement with University of Maryland, to keep up with their developments and to benefit from knowledge exchange. Outreach and communication and this phase should focus on sharing the status of the developments at relevant events and conferences.

5.1.2 Phase 2: European extension – towards self-sufficiency

Technical tasks

There are two main technical tasks planned for the second phase. The first task will be the acquisition and operation of a European owned pair of stereo sky cameras. The aim of this task is to gain knowledge and experience in operating a pair of sky cameras and to process and store the raw data. It should be ensured to keep UoM and NASA closely involved in this activity to transfer knowledge. It should also be ensured to share the data with UoM/NASA to ensure the development of a joined network.

The second task will be to setup a central cloud-based processing and data distribution structure. This task will be based on the findings of phase 1.

Further technical tasks might be identified within phase 1.

Management

Phase 1 will have shown a good maturity level of the approach, that allows for an extension of the SC network. Therefore, management in this phase should focus on liaising with ESA, CEOS and ACTRIS, to find a good way of integrating a European sky camera network into existing structures.

5.1.3 Phase 3: European roll out

Technical tasks

Once technical knowledge of operating a single site under European ownership has been gained in phase 2. The aim of the technical task of phase 3 will be to extent the SC network to approx. 10 sites. A detailed plan for technical tasks needs to be made after phase 2.

Management

The management of this phase will focus on finding European partners to operate the 10 SC sites and to transfer knowhow. Depending on the outcomes of phase 2, this might be possible through already existing networks. Further this phase should already prepare for phase 4. This means potential locations for a global sky camera network need to be identified. The involvement between Europe and US during this phase should be ensured, to prepare for a joint global network.

5.1.4 Phase 4: Global roll out

The last phase will be a global roll out. This roll out should be done in a joint activity between Europe and the US. Based on the findings of phase 3, it will be necessary to liaise with global and national networks to find partners willing to maintain a set of sky cameras. The knowledge gained during the previous three phases should be shared with the global partners.

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